

Solvent Extraction of Thorium with Liquid Cation Exchanger (Versatic 10)**

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Manuscript received 20 September 1980, revised 19 December
1981, accepted 11 March 1982

THE synthetic carboxylic acids, Versatic 911 and Versatic 10, have been shown to be a promising extractant for large scale processing of transition metals¹. A number of papers have appeared on the extraction of metals with versatic acids²⁻³ and the composition of the extracted species has also been investigated⁴⁻⁶. Flett⁷ reported its use for the extraction of metal in commercial plant. This communication reports the extraction of thorium(IV) and determination of probable composition of the extracted species using Versatic 10 in benzene as extractant. Quantitative extraction from 0.1 M acetate solution was achieved in the pH range 4.0-5.2. Thorium was separated from most of the rare earth elements, having separation factor, D_{Th}/D_M , in the order of 10^4 . The probable composition of the extracted species $ThR_{4.2}RH$ ($RH = \text{Versatic 10}$) was deduced from the extraction data.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents: Elico pH meter (Elico, Model LI-10, Hyderabad, India) was used for measurement of pH.

Versatic 10 (Shell Chemical Co., London), a mixture of branched C_{10} isomeric tertiary mono-carboxylic acids⁸, was used in conjunction with benzene, without further purification. The purity and concentration of Versatic 10 was 99% and 5.28 M, respectively.

Thorium acetate solution (1.04 mg/ml) was prepared by dissolving 3.8 g $Th(NO_3)_4 \cdot 6H_2O$ (E. Merck) in deionized water followed by precipitation of the metal hydroxide and subsequent dissolution in 0.2 M acetic acid. The solution was standardised by complexometric titration with EDTA (disodium salt) using xylenol orange indicator. All other chemicals and solvents were of analytical grade.

Extraction procedure: The aqueous phase (20 ml) containing 2.2×10^{-3} M thorium was equilibrated with 10 ml of 0.88 M Versatic 10 in benzene for 5 min. Distribution ratio reached a constant value within 2 min of shaking, so contact time of 5 min was used in all the experiments. NaOH solution was used for adjustment of pH. All the extraction experiments were carried out at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ and the ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 M with acetic acid. The two layers were allowed to settle for 5 min.

**Paper presented at the Convention of Chemist, Kurukshetra University, 1979.

The aqueous phase separated and the equilibrium pH measured. The aqueous phase was washed with 5 ml benzene to remove entrained solvent and the benzene extract was mixed with the separated organic phase. The amount of thorium present in the aqueous phase was estimated by titration with EDTA. The metal ion from the organic phase was stripped with 2N HNO_3 (20 ml) and the acid extract was washed with 5 ml benzene to remove the entrained solvent present. The amount of thorium extracted was estimated by titrating the acid extract with EDTA.

Results and Discussion

The extraction of thorium(IV) from 0.1 M acetate solution with Versatic 10 was performed at various pH. With constant extractant concentration (0.88M) and constant metal concentration (2.2×10^{-3} M) extraction of thorium increased with increased pH and became quantitative at pH 4-5.2. The optimum pH range for quantitative extraction is 4-5.2. The equilibration time was determined by varying the contact time from 0.5 min to 10 min. The distribution ratio, D, reached a constant value within 2 min and back extraction was completed within 5 min. However, contact time and stripping time was kept at 5 min in all the experiments. Various diluents, viz., benzene, toluene, xylene, carbon tetrachloride, diisopropyl ether, chloroform and butanol were tried on the extraction of thorium under the optimum conditions. Quantitative extraction of thorium was achieved in all the cases except diisopropyl ether. In case of diisopropyl ether emulsion formation took place. Some saturation experiments were undertaken at pH 4.9 to examine the practical applicability of the proposed method for large scale extraction of thorium. 25.5 g/l of thorium could be extracted (94.5%) in a single step at pH 4.9. Further increase of thorium in the aqueous phase leads to difficulty in phase separation.

Probable extraction mechanism: The acetate ion dependency on extraction was investigated by performing the extraction at constant pH, constant metal ion concentration (2.2×10^{-3} M) and constant Versatic 10 concentration (0.88M). Results show that increase of acetate ion in the aqueous phase leads to reduced extraction. This was probably due to formation of less extractable thorium acetate complexes in the aqueous phase. The plot of log D against log [acetate] was linear with a slope of -4.1, indicating the release of four acetate ions in the extraction process. The plot of log D against log [Versatic 10] was linear with a slope of 2.9. Versatic acids are known to exist as dimer in nonpolar solvent such as benzene⁹. The probable extraction mechanism, can therefore be expressed as:

where R_2H_2 represents the dimeric form of Versatic 10 in benzene and the barred species are in the organic phase.

Extractive separations: Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , La^{3+} , Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Tb^{3+} , Dy^{3+} and Hg^{2+} did not interfere in the extraction of thorium(IV). In all these cases, separations were achieved simply by controlling the pH ($pH=4.6$) of the aqueous phase during extraction. Separation factor, D_{Th}/D_M , in the order of 10^4 was achieved in all these cases. Only in the case of mercury, two consecutive equilibrations were required at pH 4.3. The interfering ions were Ce^{4+} , Pb^{2+} and U^{6+} . In order to assess the possible analytical applications, the proposed method was applied for the extraction of thorium(IV) from several synthetic mixtures prepared by mixing 5 mg of each metal [Th(IV) + Ca(II) + Ba(II); Th(IV) + La(III) + Pr(III) + Nd(III); Th(IV) + Sm(III) + Gd(III) + Tb(III); Th(IV) + Zn(II) + Cd(II) + Hg(II)]. In most of the cases quantitative recovery of thorium was achieved. Extraction experiments were carried out at pH 4.6 using 0.88 M Versatic 10 (10 ml) in benzene.

Acknowledgement

Financial support from U. G. C., New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged. The authors are thankful to Prof. A. K. De, for encouragement.

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